

Loss of Information and Classical Free Particle Action

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Classical mechanics is often concerned with the variables x and t , especially their relationship $x(t)$ in describing a moving particle. Change in p (momentum) = $\int \text{Force}(x) dx$ and Change in $\text{KE} = \int dt \text{Force}(t)$ also appear, however, and each of these integrate out one of these variables, so p is linked with x only and KE with t only. Furthermore there is information loss as $\text{KE} = p^2/2m$ is the same whether the particle moves to the left or right and $p = m_1v_1 = m_2v_2$ so with time gone one does not know the velocity. The association of KE with t for a free particle and p with x may be made stronger if one thinks in terms of probabilities i.e. $P(p_1, x)P(p_2, x) = P(p_1 + p_2, x)$ and $P(p, x_1)P(p, x_2) = P(p, x_1 + x_2)$. We argue this leads to $P(x, p) = \exp(ipx)$ and a similar result of $\exp(iEt)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$. One may then note the similarity of these two terms px and $\pm Et$ with the free particle action = Lagrangian * $t = -Et + px$ which holds for both a relativistic and nonrelativistic particle, where $v = x/t$.

Does the loss of information appear in nature? The (p, x) loss i.e. $p = m_1v_1 = m_2v_2$ does in a two-slit experiment whose solution does not require time and is calculated using $\exp(ipx)$. Thus we argue that interactions are based on p and do have a loss of information. A bound quantum state, however, has interactions with $V(x)$ and so $\exp(ipx)$ with its information loss should be present. A bound state, classical or quantum mechanical, however, has the same E_{total} at each x , so (E_{total}, t) is again a pair with x gone and loss of information means that an energy description (i.e. the time-independent Schrodinger equation) does not distinguish between forward and backwards motion. This is not needed to calculate energy values, but physically this distinct motion may exist, especially for high energy values.

Classical Mechanics

Newton's second law is formulated as a differential equation used to solve for $x(t)$, a particle's trajectory in space and time. The Lagrangian/Hamiltonian formalism also leads to the same results. Thus there is the impression of a particle's reality being linked with both x and t . This, however, is not always the case in classical mechanics as one may see:

$\int F(x)dx = \text{change in KE}$ ((1a)) and $\int F(t)dt = \text{change in } p \text{ (momentum)}$ ((1b))

((1a)) integrates out x , leaving the variable KE and t , while ((1b)) integrates out time, leaving p and x .

We argue, however, that there are consequences of integrating out either x or t . In particular, one loses information. In the case of the removal of x , one does not know if the particle moves to the right or to the left. This is fine for $\text{KE} = p^2/2m$ because it has the same value for each, but information is lost nevertheless. In the case of the loss of t , one does not know the speed so $p = m_1v_1 = m_2v_2 = m_3v_3 \dots$

One may ask: Is it possible to consider, for example, p and x without t ? We argue that a steady state reflection problem fits this scenario. A steady stream of particles with momentum p

strike a target and reflect with $-p$. The target feels an impulse of $2p$ from each particle. (One need not necessarily calculate pressure which depends on velocity i.e. flux).

Thus we argue that classical mechanics associated KE with t and p with x and that information is lost by removing either x or t in this association.

Probability

The steady stream scenario described above suggests that each x point is treated in the same way for a constant velocity. All velocities, however, lead to the same constant probability, $1/L$ for a certain length L , thus important information about the impulse proportional to p is lost. This information is critical for interactions and so, we argue, one should consider a probability based on both p and x i.e. $P(p,x)$. In such a case, p and x are both additive (conserved) type quantities so:

$$P(p_1,x)P(p_2,x)=P(p_1+p_2, x) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad P(p,x_1)P(p,x_2) = P(p,x_1+x_2) \quad ((2b))$$

$P(p,x) = a^p b^x$ does not satisfy these rules, but $P(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$ does

where $i=\sqrt{-1}$ has been introduced to avoid unlimited growth or decline and \exp has been chosen as the constant. Similar arguments should hold for KE leading to:

$$\exp(-i KE t) \text{ or } \exp(i KE t) \quad ((3))$$

We note that given the association of (p,x) and (KE,t) (for a free particle), probability yields the exact forms: px and $\pm KE t$. The consequences, however, are large in that $\exp(ipx)$ suggests that in order for p to be manifest in space, one has special wavelength regions \hbar/p and similar regions in time. If $P(p,x)$ is a probability, then $\exp(ipx)$ does not represent constant probability for each x , but rather a two dimensional probability with $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$ x -distributions. This suggests that smooth motion $x=(p/m) t$ only holds on average. Newton's second law, however, yields $v=\text{constant}$ as a solution and one does not see the unusual $\exp(ipx)$ probability. Furthermore one may use a Lagrangian L or create an action $= L t$ for a free particle and in general, one does not see $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(\pm i KE t)$. One may note, however, that in order to obtain the exponential form one had to first associate (KE,t) and (p,x) i.e. remove the "other" variable for each. We consider whether this is possible for a classical free particle action.

Classical Free Particle Action

The classical free particle action Lagrangian t is:

$$A=pp/2m t \quad \text{nonrelativistic} \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad A=-m_0 t \sqrt{1-vv} \quad \text{relativistic} \quad (c=1) \quad ((4b))$$

We wish to associate p and x and $E=KE$ and t as argued above so v is replaced with x/t . For the nonrelativistic case and for the relativistic, using symmetry to include both E and p one has:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((5))$$

This matches the result from the probability arguments using $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. One has to keep in mind, however, that this approach involves a loss of information, which we now consider.

Two Slit Interference

If one associates (p,x) with time t removed then there is a loss of information as one does not know the velocity v . Thus $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ are equivalent. Does this loss of information appear in nature? We argue it appears in a two slit experiment which only depends on $\exp(ipx)$. In other words $m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ both yield the same interference pattern. [One does not distinguish between the two.] Thus there seems to be a fundamental interaction based on impulse which occurs in nature, with the two slit form being a kind of potential $V(x)$. For a bound system with a potential $V(x)$, in order to be consistent, one would expect the form $\exp(ipx)$ to appear.

Quantum Bound State

We argue above that the form $\exp(ipx)$ should appear in a quantum bound state because it describes how a particle interacts i.e. the interaction is based on impulse. Does this mean there is no total energy or t in the picture? A bound system, both classical and quantum mechanically, should have a total constant energy. Thus (E_{total}, t) instead of (KE, t) should exist with x already being removed because E_{total} holds at all x . One then expects the form $\exp(-iEt)$. The association (E, t) , however, loses information regarding the direction of motion i.e. p and $-p$ are (pretty much) treated on the same footing. One may use $\exp(ipx)$ to describe interactions, but an energy conservation equation is needed to find the total energy. This equation should lose information about the direction of motion. (Thus we argue physical information is lost in the bound state quantum formalism.) The result is:

$$\left\{ \sum_{p} a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum_{p} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} + V(x) = E \quad ((6))$$

It is found that only discrete E satisfy ((6)) and that $a(p)=a(-p)$ or $a(p)=-a(-p)$.

Thus even though $\exp(ipx)$ is used, m (rest mass) also appears so one does know the velocity associated with each p . Interactions with $V(x)$, however, are at the p level otherwise one would not use $\exp(ipx)$.

One may note that $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \sum_{p} a(p) \exp(ipx)$ includes all p and $-p$ pairs. In the high energy limit, one might expect the particle to move first to the right and then to the left, but the quantum formalism which pairs (E, t) and (p, x) loses information. In particular, the (E, t) formalism does not distinguish between motion to the right or left for a bound state and so one may correctly calculate E_n , but $W(x)$ does not necessarily fully describe the dynamics of the problem as information (distinct forward/backward motion) has been lost.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that even though classical mechanics, in particular Newton's second law or the Lagrangian/Hamiltonian formalisms, lead to $x(t)$, there is also classical formalism which loses one of the two variables x or t . In particular, change in $KE = \int dx F(x)$ integrates out x , associating (KE, t) while change in $p = \int dt F$ integrates out t associating (p, x) . These associations lead to a loss of information. In the (E, t) case, one does not have x and so does not know in which direction the particle moves. $KE = p^2/2m$ is identical for motion to the right or left. In the (p, x) case, loss of time means one does not know velocity and so $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$. If one thinks in terms of probabilities $P(p, x)$ and $P(KE, t)$ we have argued above that $P(p, x) = \exp(ipx)$ and $P(KE, t) = \exp(\pm i KE t)$. $\exp(ipx)$ represents two dimensions of x -probability $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ which contradict $x = vt$ i.e. the latter exists only on average. $x = vt$, however, follows from Newton's laws, the Lagrangian, classical action etc. Why does one not see $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(\pm i KE t)$ in these? We argue that one may write both the nonrelativistic/relativistic classical actions as $-Et + px$. Thus one sees the (E, t) , (p, x) pairings with x and t being independent in the sense that each pairing loses one variable as well as physical information.

Does the association of say (p, x) manifest itself physically? We argue it does in a two slit experiment for which $m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$ yields the same interference pattern with time not being needed in the calculation. We argue for a time free impulse based interaction even in a quantum bound state. The quantum bound state, however, has a constant energy at each x , thus x has been removed and one has the (E, t) pairing and $\exp(-i E t)$. This pairing loses physical information about motion to the right or left, so the Schrodinger time-independent equation lacks this physical information even though it calculates energy correctly i.e. p and $-p$ or $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ appear with the same weight up to a phase:

$$\{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \ p^2/2m \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \} + V(x) = E.$$